

Assessment of Work- Life Balance in the Field of OphthalmologySana Perween¹, Amresh Kumar², Nidhi^{3*}¹JR-2, Department of Ophthalmology, Narayan Medical College, Sasaram, Bihar, India²Associate Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Narayan Medical College, Sasaram, Bihar, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Narayan Medical College, Sasaram, Bihar, India

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Abstract:**Purpose:** To assess work – life and family balance among ophthalmologist in Bihar, with significance on identifying gender differences.**Material and Methods:** A questionnaire based format was designed using forms app. The study included professional and personal life balance, gender biases, average income, career breaks, paper written and published, etc.**Results:** Among the subjects females were affected by temporary break in career (P=0.01), females earned less than males(P=0.001), males pursued fellowship unlike females(P=0.02) , female faced gender biasness at workplace unlike males(P=<0.001) these results were found to be statistically significant.**Conclusion:** Hereby it is concluded that there still exist difference in the practice pattern and personal life of male and female ophthalmologists.

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Introduction

The advancement and sustainability of the world can greatly benefit from the empowerment of women, which can be achieved through education, employment opportunities, innovation and modification of social preconceptions that limit their participation in particular professions. [1]

While women in ophthalmology saw a spike in the 19th century in several parts of the world, women in Indian ophthalmology evolved much later, but their advancement was more powerful and had a steeper slope. [2,3] Globally, women now constitute approximately 25%-30% of ophthalmologists and 35%-45% of trainees. [4]

For doctors, striking a balance between their personal and professional lives can sometimes prove to be an overwhelming undertaking. The expectation of complete dedication to their profession conflicts with personal and family responsibilities. The demands of both work and family may impede each other fulfilment, resulting in a reciprocal work- family conflict. Additionally, men and women may view the ideal work- family balance differently. In Indian society, women place a higher value on family responsibilities as a component of social identity than do males. If unresolved, this conflict may reduce doctor's job satisfaction, which may have an impact on the effectiveness of health care delivery system.

According to Dr. Carol Shields, the model of the idea work- life balance, the “5As” are accountability, availability, affability, ability and affordability. There has been increase in the number of women entering both surgical and non-surgical medical professions.¹

Legends like Dr Sudipto Pakrasi, Dr Sudha Sutaria, Dr Vasundhrara Kalevar, Gertrude Neumark Rothschild work focused on the development of material that were both biocompatible and had the optical properties necessary for use in IOL's. She developed a number of materials, including polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), which became standard material used in IOL's broke down the barriers and established the foundation for women in ophthalmology. Over time, in India and around the world, the perceptions of ophthalmology among women and the nation as a whole have evolved. For women to advance and succeed at work and at home and to fully experience life, a delicate work-life balance is necessary.

The establishment of the Women ophthalmologists society (WOS), which was founded with the intention of enhancing the professional environment, knowledge, and abilities for female ophthalmologists, developed into a platform for women to voice their concerns and find solutions to the particular problems they faced alone. This society if founded on the idea of mentorship, in which women with greater experience and seniority

mentor many mentees, inspiring them to achieve professional success and maintain a healthy work-life balance.

The community operates on the tenets of mutual support, inspiration and motivation – that is, encouraging one another before oneself.

Given that female ophthalmologists frequently need to take career pauses, the idea of short-term trainings, fellowships and observer ships has led to a notable improvement in ability. WOS has created programs, all taught by women, to educate the art of addressing crises and workplace harassment.

And one has really said well that the world’s biggest untapped talent pool is found among women. When the wind did not favour her, she stood in the storm and embellished her sails.

So this in view the study was carried out to assess work-life balance in the field of ophthalmology and opportunities available for women in ophthalmology. [5]

Methods

An internet – based cross –sectional survey with 21 questions was sent out to ophthalmologists in Bihar through social media. platform who answered the questions over the course of 72 hours covering professional and personal balance. Strict adherence to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki was maintained. 80 respondents replied with responses, which were anonymized and analysed. We saw that majority of the participants were female (51.3%), who were married (76.3%), Maximum respondent age was >40yrs, majority of the were satisfied with their career for an average working hours of 7-10hrs a day.

The questionnaire consisted of objective type questions with multiple options was given. For e.g.: age at present, career break, biases at workplace, at present practising as etc.

Statistical analyses were carried out using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) statistical software for Windows, Version (21.0). P<0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

BURN OUT WITH GENDER

CHIVALUE- 4.942
PVALUE- .08

Among the subjects maximum 26 (66.7%) males and 24 (58.5%) females were not burnt out with work and results were found to be statistically insignificant on comparing burnout with gender

GENDER

GENDER

GENDER	Frequency	Percent
MALE	39	48.8
FEMALE	41	51.3
Total	80	100.0

BURN OUT WITH WORKING HOURS

Among the subjects, maximum 11 (78.6%) in 4-6 hr, 33 (63.50%) in 7-10 hr and 6 (42.9%) in >15hr were not burn out with working hours. Results were found to be insignificant on comparing burn out with working hours.

BURN OUT WITH MARITAL STATUS

Among the subjects, maximum 11 (64.7%) unmarried were not affected with burn out. Maximum 38 (62.3%) married were not affected with burn out. Results were found to be statistically insignificant on comparing burn out with marital status.

BREAK IN CAREER WITH GENDER

Among the subjects, maximum 28 (71.8%) males were not affected by temporary break and maximum 23 (56.1%) females were affected by temporary break in career. Results were found to be statistically significant on comparing break in career with gender

INCOME WITH GENDER

Among the subjects, maximum 14 (35.9%) males having income 10-20 PA and 23 (56.1%) females having income 5-10 PA. Results were found to be statistically significant on comparing income with gender.

FELLOWSHIP WITH GENDER

Among the subjects, maximum 27 (69.2%) males pursuing fellowship and maximum 23 (56.10%) females were not pursuing fellowship. Results were found to be statistically significant on comparing fellowship with gender.

Among the subjects maximum 33(84.6%) males were not facing bias and 27(65.9%) females were facing bias. Results were found to be statistically highly significant on comparing bias with gender.

BURN OUT WITH PRESENT PRACTICE

CHIVALUE- 3.112
PVALUE- .53

Among the subjects, maximum 31 (60.8%) practicing comprehensive ophthalmology were not burnt out. Maximum 14 (60.9%) practicing cataract/ anterior segment were not burnt out and maximum 5 (83.3%) practicing sub speciality were not burnt out. Results were found to be statistically insignificant on comparing burn out with present practice.

CAREER SATISFACTION WITH GENDER

CHIVALUE- 1.867
PVALUE- .39

Among the subjects, maximum 29 (74.4%) males were satisfied with career and 25 (61%) females were satisfied with career. Results were found to be insignificant on comparing career satisfaction with gender.

BURN OUT WITH FAMILY TIME AFFECTED

CHIVALUE- 4.253
PVALUE- .37

Among the subjects, maximum 29 (54.5%) were affected family time with no burn out and 21 (77.8%) were not affected family time with no burn out. Results were found to statistically insignificant on comparing burn out with family time affected.

females face gender bias

■ females face gender bias

Discussion

The challenge of balancing professional goals and personal life often proves to be a daunting task for female ophthalmologists. The number of women joining surgical as well as nonsurgical medical specialities has been increasing. This development is liable to influence the work- family balance and work satisfaction of the health care delivery workforce. Ophthalmology is no different from other medical specialities and it is encountering similar increase in the number of female practitioners.

In this present study males were 48.7% and females were 51.3%. In this present study females were more in comparison to males and results were in contrast to study conducted by Saurabh Kumar et al in which males were maximum i.e. 65.7% in comparison to female were 34.3% respectively and Jinapriya D et al in which males were n=72 and females were n= 65 respectively.

In this present study majority i.e. 76.3% females were married and 21.2% were unmarried respectively and similar results were seen in study conducted Farah Naaz Fathima et al in which majority i.e. 69.3% females were married and 29.6% females were unmarried.

In this present study 56.1% females were earning average 5-10 lakhs PA. similar results were seen in study conducted by Helen V Danesh-Meyer et al in which 52.5% females were earning 5-10 lakhs PA and results were in contrast to study conducted by Saurabh Kumar et al in which 53.4% females were earning 10-20 lakh PA. [5,6]

In our study 65.9% females faced gender bias. Similar results were seen in study conducted by Saurabh Kumar et al in which 60.8% females face gender bias respectively.

In this present study 61% females satisfied with career. However, similar results were seen in study conducted by Saurabh Kumar et al and Sharma Mohita in which 56.5% and 52.5% females were satisfied with career respectively and Jinapriya D et al. [5,7]

In this present study 56.1% females had taken temporary break in career. However similar results were seen in study conducted by Sharma Mohita et al and Farah Naaz Fathima et al in which 49% and 51.7% females had taken temporary break in career.

In this present study, 65% females worked 7-10hrs and only 17.5% females worked for 4-6hrs per day and similar results were seen in study conducted by Sharma Mohita et al in which 54.8% females worked 7-10 hrs and 26.1% females worked for 4-6hrs per day. In contrast there were no difference found in working hours per week in relation to gender in Jinapriya D et al.

In this present study , 43.9% females pursuing fellowship after post- graduation and results were in contrast to study conducted by Sharma Mohita et al in which 62.9% females pursuing fellowship after post- graduation.

In this present study females Ophthalmologists were slightly more burnt out in comparison to males. Females working 7-10hrs were slightly more burnt out in comparison to males. Present study showed that there is no effect of marital status on burnout. In this study female's Ophthalmologists were burnt out on practicing comprehensive ophthalmologists. So far there has been no study conducted on there burnout relations with gender, working hours, marital status and present practise.

The concept of women ophthalmology as separate societies nationally and internationally is not to

create an isolated subset or to provide a gender – based difference, but to encourage women to get out of their comfort zone and stand up in today’s world with widespread equality, for what they believe in the most – Passion for Ophthalmology, for a brighter tomorrow.

Conclusion

Hereby it is concluded that there still exist difference in the practice pattern and personal life of male and female ophthalmologists.

Despite the advancing world, females facing biasness at their work place still remains the point of concern.

However both male and female didn’t felt burnout with long working hours.

Female balanced both personal and professional life very well even though they had to take a break in their career and they were satisfied with their career even with less income than male.

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